

Recent Progress in Microneedle Drug Delivery Technology and Its Implications in Transdermal Cancer Therapy

Ananya Nagar^a, Swati Prakash^a, Shradha Bisht^b, Vishakha Jaiswal^{*a}

^aAmity Institute of Pharmacy, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus,
Uttar Pradesh, India-226028.

^bCollege of Pharmacy, Shivalik Campus, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India- 248197.

*Corresponding author

Dr. Vishakha Jaiswal

Abstract

Microneedles (MNs) are emerging as a transformative tool in the treatment of cancer, offering a minimally invasive approach for localized drug delivery. Their potential lies in their ability to bypass traditional barriers like the skin and mucosa, allowing direct administration of therapeutic agents into target tissues. This technology can be particularly advantageous in overcoming chemoresistance, a significant hurdle in cancer therapy, by enhancing drug penetration and enabling sustained release of chemotherapeutics. MNs can deliver a wide range of anticancer agents directly into tumor microenvironments, including small molecules, nanoparticles, and biologicals like antibodies and RNA therapeutics. Furthermore, microneedle-mediated delivery systems are being explored for combination therapies, where they enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy when used alongside immunotherapeutic or targeted drugs. In particular, smart MNs equipped with stimuli-responsive or biodegradable materials enable precision drug release in response to changes in the tumor microenvironment, potentially reducing off-target effects and minimizing toxicity. This review highlights recent advances in MN-based cancer therapies, focusing on their role in overcoming chemoresistance mechanisms such as efflux pump activation, DNA repair pathways, and apoptotic resistance. MN systems can be integrated with personalized medicine strategies for patient-specific benefits to maximize their therapeutic potential in oncological applications.

Keywords: *Cancer Therapy, Chemoresistance, Drug Delivery, Microneedles, Targeted Therapy, Tumor Microenvironment,*

1. Introduction

Microneedles, typically comprising patches with tiny needles, have garnered attention for their transdermal application in diagnosing and treating various diseases, including cancer. These patches provide several benefits, such as improved treatment efficiency, self-administration, painless application, and being more economical and eco-friendlier compared to traditional therapies [1]. Recent studies have explored techniques like PROTAC (proteolysis-targeting chimera), where microneedles play a crucial role in cancer treatment. However, to avoid cytotoxic effects, it is essential to prevent the degradation of proteins in healthy tissues[2]. PROTAC leverages the cell's natural protein degradation mechanism to eliminate harmful proteins, making it a promising strategy for small molecule-based cancer treatment [3]. Microneedles can penetrate the immune cell-rich epidermis, stimulating T cells within the tumor microenvironment [4]. Although transdermal systems have limitations (such as limited drug permeability, skin Irritation, and sensitization, variable absorption, etc.), microneedles overcome these by puncturing the skin barrier, enabling the delivery of various drugs into the dermal layer. This technique is advancing in pre-clinical studies for chemotherapy, photothermal therapy, and immunotherapy [5]. Furthermore, microneedles are being developed for cancer vaccines, early diagnosis, and clinical trials to assess safety and efficacy [6,7].

General Properties of Microneedles and classification of microneedle

1.1. Properties of microneedle

- Microneedles are micron-sized devices used for localized delivery of therapeutic agents [8].
- Microneedles typically range from 52 to 250 micrometers in width and can extend up to 1500 micrometers in length [8,9].
- Microneedles composed of materials like stainless steel and titanium, offering excellent mechanical strength and biocompatibility, they are non-degradable and cost-effective[10].
- Polymers used in microneedles are flexible, biocompatible, cost-effective, and suitable for large-scale production, used in drug delivery and biosensing.
- Microneedles can deliver small molecules like doxorubicin and macromolecules such as proteins (ovalbumin) or nanoparticles.
- The composition of microneedles is crucial for determining medication encapsulation, release, stability, and therapeutic efficacy [11].
- Materials like stainless steel, titanium, glass, and polymers are used for microneedle fabrication via different methods [12].

1.2. Types of microneedles

1.2.1. Solid microneedles

Solid microneedles are used to pre-treat the skin by creating micron-sized channels, enhancing drug permeation into the skin layers, leading to systemic or local therapeutic effects upon drug patch application [13]. They facilitate drug delivery through passive diffusion into the skin. Narayan *et al.* developed microneedles using tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide etching, with a length of 158 μm and a base of 110.5 μm [14–16]. Further, they fabricated gold-coated solid silicon microneedles with a 250 μm height, 52.8 μm base width, and an aspect ratio of 4.73.

1.2.2. Hollow Microneedle

Hollow microneedles have a hollow space filled with pharmaceutical agents, allowing for direct delivery to the skin's topmost layer through holes at the tip. They are primarily used for high molecular weight drugs like proteins, oligonucleotides, and vaccines. Hollow microneedles can administer small amounts of vaccines to the epidermis in a self-regulating manner, overcoming the disadvantages of solid microneedles [16]. Suzuki and his team fabricated parathyroid hormone (PTH) that mimicked structured microneedles, enhancing skin permeation [17].

1.2.3. Dissolving Microneedle

These microneedles, made from bio-conformable polymers (such as hyaluronic acid (HA), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC,)) dissolve in the skin to release drugs, ensuring long-term therapy with enhanced patient compliance[18]. Chen developed tip-dissolving microneedles for fast drug delivery[19].

1.2.4. Hydrogel-Forming Microneedle

Hydrogel-forming microneedles, made from super-swelling hydrophilic polymers, swell in the skin due to interstitial fluid, offering flexibility in shape and size. They allow for easy sterilization and removal[20]. Migdadi *et al.* developed these microneedles to deliver metformin trans-dermally, improving drug permeation and bioavailability [21].

Several microneedle types and their utilization in the cancer are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1. Types of microneedles and their utilization in cancer

Microneedle Types	Material	API	Features in Cancer	Application	Reference
Solid Microneedles	Stainless Steel, Titanium, Ceramics	Paclitaxel / Doxorubicin	Microchannels based drug delivery	Breast Cancer	[22]
Hollow Microneedles	Silicon or glass	Doxorubicin, Cisplatin, or Immunotherapeutics (Interleukins)	Direct delivery of liquid drugs into the dermis	Melanoma	[23]
Coated Microneedles	Polymer coatings (Polyvinylpyrrolidone, Carboxymethylcellulose)	DNA vaccines, siRNA, or Monoclonal-antibodies (Nivolumab)	Quick release of API in vaccination and gene therapy	Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)	[24]
Dissolvable Microneedles	Biodegradable polymers hyaluronic acid, polyvinyl alcohol, or polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA)	Gemcitabine and 5-FU	Dissolution releases drug into dermis	Skin cancer	[25]
Hydrogel-forming Microneedles	Hydrophilic polymers (Polyvinyl alcohol, Chitosan, or Carboxymethylcellulose)	Cisplatin / Doxorubicin	Swell upon insertion and regulate the drug release	Cervical cancer	[26]

Fig. 1 Mechanism of Action of Different Microneedles: (a) This Section Shows the Skin-Insertion of Different Types of Microneedles (b) This Section Shows the Delivery of Drugs by Microneedles[27].

1.3. Materials used for the preparation of microneedle

Various types of materials are used for the preparation of microneedles some of the materials are silicon, polymer, ceramic, and many more.

1.3.1. Silicon

In the 1990s, silicon was used to construct the first microneedles due to its crystal-like structure and elastic moduli of 50-180 gigapascal (GPa)[28]. While it allows for precise manufacturing in various sizes, silicon's high cost, complex fabrication, and biocompatibility issues limit its widespread use in microneedles[29,30].

1.3.2. Metal

Stainless steel, titanium, palladium, nickel, and palladium-cobalt alloys are commonly used for microneedles, offering favorable mechanical properties and biocompatibility compared to silicon, despite some toxicity concerns[28,31]. Fabrication techniques like photochemical etching, electroplating, and laser cutting are employed[30]. However, metal microneedles have limitations, such as non-degradability and inflexibility[32,33].

1.3.3. Ceramic

Aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) is primarily used for its resistance to chemical reactions, owing to its durable oxide layer formed by strong ionic and covalent bonds between aluminum and oxygen atoms[34]. Other ceramics, such as gypsum and brushite, are employed[29]. Ormocer®, an organically modified ceramic, has emerged as a versatile material. However, Al₂O₃ microneedles may break upon manual insertion into the skin, indicating fragility[35]. Dual replication processes, using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) molds and ceramic sintering, ensure robust microneedle arrays, which show durability in controlled micro-indentation tests[36].

1.4. Fabrication techniques

Fabrication techniques refer to the processes and methods used to design and create microneedles depending upon several factors such as specific shapes, sizes, and functionalities using materials like metals, polymers, or ceramics. The criteria for the selection of fabrication methods (refer to Figure 2) for various types of microneedles rely on the types of the microneedle [37].

Fig. 2 Various Fabrication Techniques of Microneedle[38]

1.5. Evaluation Parameters

Various evaluation parameters are used to evaluate the performance of microneedles such as morphology drug release, *in-vitro* skin permeation studies, and *in-vivo* studies, are mentioned in the table below.

Table 2. Various evaluation parameters of Microneedles

Evaluation Method	Equipment/ Techniques	Reference
Characterization Techniques	Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), thermal analysis, polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, and many more.	[39]
<i>In Vitro</i> Skin Penetration	Franz diffusion cells through Artificial skin models or excised human/animal skin	[40]
<i>In Vitro</i> Drug Release	Drug release kinetics of microneedles is assessed using diffusion studies in simulated body fluids, such as phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) or plasma.	[40]
<i>In Vivo</i> Efficacy Studies	Trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL) is measured with Delfin Vapometer.	[40]

Dimension and Insertion	Compression tests and finite element modelling assess insertion force and mechanical strength.	[41]
Biocompatibility and Safety	Histological analysis, cytokine profiling, and safety biomarkers.	[42]
Immunogenic Response Studies	ELISA, flow cytometry, and antibody titration assays.	[43]

Tiny, microscopic needles can permeate through the skin's outer barrier, delivering medications directly into deeper skin layers for better absorption and effectiveness. This approach is minimally invasive, painless, and may help patients follow treatment plans more consistently. By bypassing the skin's tough outer layer, these microneedles significantly improve how drugs penetrate compared to regular skin patches. When combined with techniques using electrical current or sound waves, drug delivery can be even more effective, working with many medications, including larger molecular compounds. The microneedle patches are being designed for simple use, enabling patients to apply them without medical help. Research is expanding their use across various medical fields, including for managing long-term conditions like cancer [44-46].

2. Microneedles involved in anticancer therapies

2.1. Chemotherapy

Chemotherapy is a common treatment for tumors, but it faces challenges like systemic side effects and poor targeting. Microneedles (MNs) offer a novel strategy to overcome these issues by enabling transdermal delivery of anticancer drugs[47]. Banga *et al.* demonstrated solid MNs for methotrexate (MTX) delivery, enhancing its release through sol-gel transition [48–50].

2.1.1. Microneedles in Combating Chemoresistance

Chemoresistance (CR) is a major driver of cancer treatment failure and there is an intensive effort in fighting CR cancers. CR is also a major hurdle in oncology, which results in tumor recurrence and treatment failure. It begins from multiple molecular and cellular mechanisms including the activation of efflux pumps, improved DNA repairing systems, and apoptosis resistance that together diminish the efficacy of traditional chemotherapeutic agents. So, to overcome that type of resistance we need some novel or powerful technique and microneedles are one of them [51,52]. Microneedles (MNs) are a type of newly emerging transdermal drug delivery system, which can also be applied to overcome some clinical hurdles such as chemoresistance in cancers and selective killing of cancer cells without damaging normal cells. MNs provide a less invasive approach by delivery of drugs directly to tumor tissues or into the systemic circulation and widely evade several physiological barriers such as skin, mucosal layers, and extracellular matrix[53,54]. Several roles of microneedles in overcoming chemoresistance molecular and cellular mechanisms are mentioned in Table 3.

Table 3. Role of Microneedle in Overcoming Chemoresistance Mechanisms

Mechanism	Description	Role of Microneedles (MNs)	Examples	References
Efflux-Pump Activation and Multidrug Resistance (MDR)	Overexpression of efflux pumps, including P-glycoprotein (P-gp) and multidrug resistance-associated proteins (MRPs) actively expels chemotherapeutic agents and decreases intracellular drug levels, failing cytotoxic treatment.	MNs also jointly administer efflux pump inhibitors with chemotherapeutics for improved intracellular drug accumulation and cytotoxicity.	Verapamil, Tariquidar	[55]
DNA Repair Mechanisms	Cancer cells up-regulate DNA repair systems (homologous recombination [HR], base excision repair) as a means to cope with chemotherapy-induced DNA damage to survive and proliferate.	MNs can directly deliver DNA repair inhibitors into the tumor area to sensitize cancer cells to chemotherapy and at the same time alleviates systemic toxicity and off-target effects.	PARP inhibitors (e.g., Olaparib)	[56]
Resistance to Apoptosis	Resist apoptosis, cancer cells either dysregulate intrinsic apoptotic pathways, as is the case with Bcl-2 family proteins, or they tend to overexpress anti-apoptotic molecules or downregulate pro-apoptotic factors.	MNs can deliver pro-apoptotic agents, such as BH3 mimetics or anti-apoptotic protein inhibitors locally permitting effective restoration of apoptotic	BH3-mimetics, Caspase activators	[57]

		sensitivity and enhanced chemotherapy efficacy.		
Tumor Microenvironment (TME) Barriers	Drug penetration is impeded by the tumor microenvironment (TME), which traditionally is perceived as a hypoxic, acidic, and high interstitial pressure tissue and leads to chemoresistance.	MNs achieve direct delivery of the drug into TME, overcoming the physical and biochemical barriers. They may create agents that modulate the TME to increase dissemination and decrease drug resistance.	Anti-angiogenic drugs, Matrix metalloproteinase inhibitors	[58,59]

2.2. Immune therapies

Cancer-based therapies aim to stimulate the host's immune system for targeted anti-tumor responses [8,60]. Photoimmunotherapy and peptide-based therapies prepare the immune system to target tumor-related antigens, helping clear cancerous cells. Skin-targeted vaccine delivery activates antigen-presenting cells (APCs) like macrophages and dendritic cells, stimulating T and B cells for a systemic immune reaction [61,62]. Zaric *et al.* developed microneedles with PLGA nanoparticles encapsulating ovalbumin for an antigen-specific immune response against melanoma tumors. A microneedle platform combining photodynamic therapy and immunotherapy delivers both a photosensitizer and an anti-CTLA4 antibody [63,64].

2.3. Gene therapies

Microneedles are used for delivering antitumor gene therapies, such as plasmid DNA (pDNA) or nanoparticles. Ali *et al.* developed a polyvinylpyrrolidone-based microneedle patch loaded with E6/E7 pDNA RALA nanoparticles for cervical cancer treatment [65]. This minimally invasive approach delivers genetic constructs directly into skin tissue, overcoming the stratum corneum barrier. Zhou *et al.* formulated nanoparticles containing p53 plasmid DNA and developed microneedles for their delivery. That is because the p53 gene, known as the "guardian of the genome," is vital for tumor suppression and inducing apoptosis. Using the microneedles, pDNA was topically delivered to melanoma tumors in a mouse model, resulting in marked tumor regression and improved immune-mediated tumor rejection [66,67].

3. Microneedle as a Vaccine Delivery for Cancer Therapy

Microneedles offer a promising method for cancer vaccine delivery, targeting the skin's immune cells to enhance the immune response. Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), like immune checkpoint inhibitors, have limitations, but incorporating anti-PD1 into pH-responsive microneedles enables precise localized delivery. There are several microneedles vaccines some of which are mentioned below.

3.1. Antigen vaccine

Dendritic cells (DCs) are crucial for inducing immune responses, and appropriate activation and antigen presentation to these cells are important for T cell-mediated long-lasting immunity through transdermal vaccination [68,69]. MN-mediated transdermal vaccination has shown great potential for cancer immunotherapy [70]. Studies have demonstrated that MNs deliver ovalbumin (OVA) effectively to the skin, achieving maximal plasma concentration within 1 hour and stable release for over 6 hours. MNs create an antigen depot for continuous release over several days, resulting in stronger antibody responses compared to intramuscular injection. Successful immunization requires proper optimization of MNs and antigen-adjuvant formulations [71–73]. Fujiyama *et al.* confirmed the effectiveness of transdermal immunization in melanoma patients by activating dendritic cells and cytotoxic T lymphocytes, leading to improved anticancer outcomes [74].

3.2. Gene vaccine

In recent years, gene therapy has shown promise in treating diseases like cancer [75]. For gene vaccination to be effective, delivered genes must remain active within cells and express the correct promoter to initiate an immune response [76]. However, issues like low stability and fast clearance limit clinical use. Microneedle (MN)-based transdermal gene immunization addresses these limitations [77,78]. Pearton *et al.* showed that MNs efficiently load pDNA, increasing stability and successfully translating reporter genes both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Various MN materials have been explored for gene-related immune responses, including nanoparticle pDNA vaccines and CNT-based systems [79,80].

4. Applications of microneedle in various cancer

Microneedles have been used in various cancers due to their ability to deliver drugs via transdermal and intradermal routes with minimal invasiveness. Collection of micro-needles enables localized delivery of chemotherapeutic agents, immune checkpoint inhibitors and gene therapies, which enhances therapeutic efficacy while minimizing systemic toxicity. The tumor suppression is enhanced for melanoma microneedles to improve penetration of anticancer drugs doxorubicin and paclitaxel. For breast and cervical cancers, dissolution microneedles the nanoparticles/immunotherapeutics provide controlled and sustained drug release, improving patient compliance and treatment outcomes [81]. Some applications of microneedles in the treatment of various types of cancer are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Microneedle Technology in Cancer Therapeutics

API	Polymer	Benefits	Application	Reference
Doxorubicin (Breast Cancer)	Polyvinyl-alcohol (PVA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhances local drug accumulation, Reduces systemic toxicity, Extends the duration 	Targeted delivery in API and vaccines in breast cancer	[82]
Anti-PD1 and Ovalbumin (Melanoma)	Polyvinyl-pyrrolidone (PVP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Targets skin dendritic cells Enhances anti-tumor immunity 	Deliver immune checkpoint inhibitors like anti-PD1 for local melanoma treatment.	[83]
Plasmid DNA (Cervical cancer)	Chitosan-coated microneedles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protects pdna from degradation, facilitates in-situ antigen expression. Enhances immune responses 	Gene therapy and DNA vaccines for cervical cancer are delivered via microneedles using plasmid DNA against HPV-related cervical cancer.	[84]
Anti-PD1 (Lung cancer)	Hyaluronic acid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improves drug stability, retention, and Tumor-suppressing ability 	Local delivery of anti-programmed cell death protein-1 (anti-PD1) antibodies for lung cancer, controlling drug release directly at lung tumor sites.	[85]

5. Clinical aspects of Microneedles

While microneedle therapies show promise, the need for more robust preclinical and clinical trials (Table 5) remains critical to fully establish their efficacy and safety in broader cancer treatment. Preclinical studies have demonstrated the ability of microneedles to deliver both small and large molecules effectively, with ongoing research into their application for various cancer types. Recent studies indicate that microneedles can improve drug bioavailability and reduce systemic toxicity, making it a promising adjunct to existing therapies.

Table 5. Microneedle based formulations in clinical trials [86]

NCT NO.	Investigational Drug	Sponsor	Start date	End date	Phase of clinical	Conditions
NCT05377905	Microneedle Array Doxorubicin (MNA-D)	Falo, Louis, MD	Sept-2023	March-2023	Phase 2	Skin Cancer-Squamous Cell Carcinoma
NCT01812837	Aminolevulinic Acid Radiation: Blue light	University of California	July-2012	March-2014	Not applicable	Actinic keratosis
NCT05329532	Pembrolizumab Device: MicronJet600™ microneedle device (NanoPass)	Scancell Ltd	April-2022	June-2026	Phase 2	Triple Negative Breast cancer, Renal cancer, High Grade Ovarian serous, Adenocarcinoma, Squamous cell carcinoma of the Head and neck
NCT04928222	Doxorubicin-containing Microneedle Array	Skin Ject, Inc	Sept-2021	Dec-2023	Phase 2	Basal cell carcinoma

NCT02632110	Levulan Kerastick (Aminolevulinic Acid HCl) for Topical Solution, 20%	DUSA Pharmaceuticals, Inc	March-2016	Sept-2016	Phase 2	Actinic keratosis
-------------	---	---------------------------	------------	-----------	---------	-------------------

6. Challenges and Future Directions

Moving from lab research to large-scale production of dissolvable microneedle arrays hits several roadblocks. Manufacturing is tough due to the absence of uniform production techniques, leading to inconsistent quality and hindering the ability to increase output. Choosing materials like polymers, ceramics, or metals adds to the complexity and cost, as each needs specific handling. Plus, there aren't many contract manufacturers who can handle microneedle arrays, making scaling up difficult. Concerns about regulations and the need for strict quality control also make investors hesitant. However, a developing regulatory framework seeks to smooth this transition by offering clearer manufacturing guidelines [87]. Microneedle technology holds immense potential in revolutionizing cancer therapy due to its ability to offer targeted, minimally invasive drug delivery. Future research will focus on developing even more precise targeting mechanisms, such as using microneedles functionalized with specific ligands that bind to cancer cells. Also, Advancements in 3D printing and microfabrication techniques will enable the production of personalized microneedle arrays.

7. Conclusions

MN-assisted drug delivery systems demonstrate a novel method in cancer therapy, showcasing clear advantages including improved drug bioavailability, decreased side effects, and sustained release profiles. By avoiding biological barriers such as the stratum corneum, these systems overcome significant shortcomings of conventional therapies and allow localized drug administration. Nonetheless, low drug loading quantity, inadequate penetration depth into deeper tumors, and skin irritation are still hindrances. The future, such as the development of nanotechnology, smart materials, and combinatorial therapies, will make it possible for the next breakthrough to address these challenges on the horizon. Future advancements include biodegradable MNs, stimuli-responsive drug release mechanisms, and personalized drug formulations based on individual genetic profiles, which will improve MN-assisted cancer treatments in terms of both efficacy and safety. MN technology helps fill these gaps and is destined to play an important role in shaping future personalized, minimally invasive, and highly specific oncological treatments.

8. List of Abbreviations

MN's: Microneedles, **5-FU:** 5-Fluoro Uracil, **API:** Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients, **PLGA:** Poly Lactic Glycolic Acid, **PVA:** Poly Vinyl Alcohol, **PVP:** Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone, **CMC:** Carboxy Methyl Cellulose, **DNA:** Deoxyribonucleic Acid, **IL:** Interleukins, **NSCLC:** Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer, **siRNA:** Small Interfering Ribo Nucleic Acid, **GPa:** Gigapascal, **Al₂O₃:** Aluminum Oxide, **PDMS:** Polydimethylsiloxane, **AFM:** Atomic Force Microscopy.

9. Reference

- [1] Ganeson K, Alias AH, Murugaiyah V, Amirul A-AA, Ramakrishna S, Vigneswari S. Microneedles for Efficient and Precise Drug Delivery in Cancer Therapy. *Pharmaceutics* 2023;15:744. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15030744>.
- [2] Huang J, Yao Z, Li B, Ping Y. Targeted delivery of PROTAC-based prodrug activated by bond-cleavage bioorthogonal chemistry for microneedle-assisted cancer therapy. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2023;361:270–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2023.07.062>.
- [3] Fan L, Tong W, Wei A, Mu X. Progress of proteolysis-targeting chimeras (PROTACs) delivery system in tumor treatment. *Int J Biol Macromol* 2024;275:133680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.133680>.
- [4] Lan X, Zhu W, Huang X, Yu Y, Xiao H, Jin L, et al. Microneedles loaded with anti-PD-1–cisplatin nanoparticles for synergistic cancer immuno-chemotherapy. *Nanoscale* 2020;12:18885–98. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0NR04213G>.
- [5] Li D, Hu D, Xu H, Patra HK, Liu X, Zhou Z, et al. Progress and perspective of microneedle system for anti-cancer drug delivery. *Biomaterials* 2021;264:120410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2020.120410>.

- [6] Singh V, Kesharwani P. Recent advances in microneedles-based drug delivery device in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2021;338:394–409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.08.054>.
- [7] Seetharam AA, Choudhry H, Bakhrebah MA, Abdulaal WH, Gupta MS, Rizvi SMD, et al. Microneedles Drug Delivery Systems for Treatment of Cancer: A Recent Update. *Pharmaceutics* 2020;12:1101. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics1211101>.
- [8] Moreira AF, Rodrigues CF, Jacinto TA, Miguel SP, Costa EC, Correia IJ. Microneedle-based delivery devices for cancer therapy: A review. *Pharmacol Res* 2019;148:104438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2019.104438>.
- [9] Bhatnagar S, Dave K, Venuganti VVK. Microneedles in the clinic. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2017;260:164–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2017.05.029>.
- [10] Garg M, Jain N, Kaul S, Rai VK, Nagaich U. Recent advancements in the expedition of microneedles: from lab worktops to diagnostic care centers. *Microchimica Acta* 2023;190:301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-023-05859-z>.
- [11] Huang Y, Yu H, Wang L, Shen D, Ni Z, Ren S, et al. Research progress on cosmetic microneedle systems: Preparation, property and application. *Eur Polym J* 2022;163:110942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2021.110942>.
- [12] Ullah A, Kim CM, Kim GM. Porous polymer coatings on metal microneedles for enhanced drug delivery. *R Soc Open Sci* 2018;5:171609. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171609>.
- [13] Aldawood FK, Andar A, Desai S. A Comprehensive Review of Microneedles: Types, Materials, Processes, Characterizations and Applications. *Polymers (Basel)* 2021;13:2815. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13162815>.
- [14] Li J, Zeng M, Shan H, Tong C. Microneedle Patches as Drug and Vaccine Delivery Platform. *Curr Med Chem* 2017;24. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867324666170526124053>.
- [15] Prausnitz MR. Engineering Microneedle Patches for Vaccination and Drug Delivery to Skin. *Annu Rev Chem Biomol Eng* 2017;8:177–200. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-chembioeng-060816-101514>.
- [16] Pradeep Narayanan S, Raghavan S. Solid silicon microneedles for drug delivery applications. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 2017;93:407–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-016-9698-6>.
- [17] Pradeep Narayanan S, Raghavan S. Fabrication and characterization of gold-coated solid silicon microneedles with improved biocompatibility. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 2019;104:3327–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-018-2596-3>.
- [18] Ita K. Transdermal Delivery of Drugs with Microneedles—Potential and Challenges. *Pharmaceutics* 2015;7:90–105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics7030090>.
- [19] Chen J, Huang W, Huang Z, Liu S, Ye Y, Li Q, et al. Fabrication of Tip-Dissolving Microneedles for Transdermal Drug Delivery of Meloxicam. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 2018;19:1141–51. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-017-0926-7>.
- [20] Donnelly RF, Singh TRR, Alkilani AZ, McCrudden MTC, O'Neill S, O'Mahony C, et al. Hydrogel-forming microneedle arrays exhibit antimicrobial properties: Potential for enhanced patient safety. *Int J Pharm* 2013;451:76–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2013.04.045>.
- [21] Kim Y-C, Park J-H, Prausnitz MR. Microneedles for drug and vaccine delivery. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 2012;64:1547–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2012.04.005>.
- [22] Uddin MJ, Scoutaris N, Klepetsanis P, Chowdhry B, Prausnitz MR, Douroumis D. Inkjet printing of transdermal microneedles for the delivery of anticancer agents. *Int J Pharm* 2015;494:593–602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2015.01.038>.
- [23] Donnelly RF, Prausnitz MR. The promise of microneedle technologies for drug delivery. *Drug Deliv Transl Res* 2024;14:573–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13346-023-01430-8>.

- [24] Kumar Sarella PN, Valluri S, Vegi S, Vendi VK, Vipparthi AK. Microneedle Arrays: Advancements, Applications and Future Prospects in Pharmaceutical Delivery. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Technology* 2024;229–36. <https://doi.org/10.52711/2231-5713.2024.00038>.
- [25] Desai VM, Priya S, Gorantla S, Singhvi G. Revolutionizing Therapeutic Delivery with Microneedle Technology for Tumor Treatment. *Pharmaceutics* 2022;15:14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15010014>.
- [26] Zang C, Tian Y, Tang Y, Tang M, Yang D, Chen F, et al. Hydrogel-based platforms for site-specific doxorubicin release in cancer therapy. *J Transl Med* 2024;22:879. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-024-05490-3>.
- [27] Desai VM, Priya S, Gorantla S, Singhvi G. Revolutionizing Therapeutic Delivery with Microneedle Technology for Tumor Treatment. *Pharmaceutics* 2022;15:14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15010014>.
- [28] S.B.V.J. C, Mannayee G. Structural analysis and simulation of solid microneedle array for vaccine delivery applications. *Mater Today Proc* 2022;65:3774–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.06.483>.
- [29] Cheng W, Wang X, Zou S, Ni M, Lu Z, Dai L, et al. Fabrication of Black Silicon Microneedle Arrays for High Drug Loading. *J Funct Biomater* 2023;14:245. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jfb14050245>.
- [30] Faraji Rad Z, Prewett PD, Davies GJ. An overview of microneedle applications, materials, and fabrication methods. *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology* 2021;12:1034–46. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.12.77>.
- [31] Guo Y, Zhang C, Xie B, Xu W, Rao Z, Zhou P, et al. Multifunctional Microneedle Patch Based on Metal-Phenolic Network with Photothermal Antimicrobial, ROS Scavenging, Immunomodulatory, and Angiogenesis for Programmed Treatment of Diabetic Wound Healing. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* 2024;16:33205–22. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.4c07091>.
- [32] Chen J, Niu H, Guan L, Yang Z, He Y, Zhao J, et al. Microneedle-Assisted Transdermal Delivery of 2D Bimetallic Metal–Organic Framework Nanosheet-Based Cascade Biocatalysts for Enhanced Catalytic Therapy of Melanoma. *Adv Healthc Mater* 2023;12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.202202474>.
- [33] Luo X, Yang L, Cui Y. Microneedles: materials, fabrication, and biomedical applications. *Biomed Microdevices* 2023;25:20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10544-023-00658-y>.
- [34] González-Méndez I, Sorroza-Martínez K, Rivera E. Types of microneedles for drug delivery. *Design and Applications of Microneedles in Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, Elsevier; 2024, p. 65–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-443-13881-2.00018-7>.
- [35] Jafarzadeh M, Adnan R, Mazlan MKN. Thermal stability and optical property of ormocers (organically modified ceramics) nanoparticles produced from copolymerization between amino-silanes and tetraethoxysilane. *J Non Cryst Solids* 2012;358:2981–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnoncrystol.2012.07.028>.
- [36] Gittard SD, Narayan RJ, Jin C, Ovsianikov A, Chichkov BN, Monteiro-Riviere NA, et al. Pulsed laser deposition of antimicrobial silver coating on Ormocer® microneedles. *Biofabrication* 2009;1:041001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1758-5082/1/4/041001>.
- [37] Li J, Zeng M, Shan H, Tong C. Microneedle Patches as Drug and Vaccine Delivery Platform. *Curr Med Chem* 2017;24. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867324666170526124053>.
- [38] Faraji Rad Z, Prewett PD, Davies GJ. An overview of microneedle applications, materials, and fabrication methods. *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology* 2021;12:1034–46. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.12.77>.
- [39] Puri A, Nguyen HX, Tijani AO, Banga AK. Characterization of Microneedles and Microchannels for Enhanced Transdermal Drug Delivery. *Ther Deliv* 2021;12:77–103. <https://doi.org/10.4155/tde-2020-0096>.
- [40] Iapichino M, Maibach H, Stoeber B. Quantification methods comparing in vitro and in vivo percutaneous permeation by microneedles and passive diffusion. *Int J Pharm* 2023;638:122885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2023.122885>.

- [41] Villota I, Calvo PC, Campo OI, Rico FF. Microneedle, a one-plane bevel-tipped fabrication by 3D printing process. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1490579/v1>.
- [42] Gad SE, Gad SC. Biocompatibility. *Encyclopedia of Toxicology*, Elsevier; 2024, p. 91–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824315-2.01099-X>.
- [43] Swanson SJ, Bussiere J. Immunogenicity assessment in non-clinical studies. *Curr Opin Microbiol* 2012;15:337–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2012.05.015>.
- [44] Zhao Z, Chen Y, Shi Y. Microneedles: a potential strategy in transdermal delivery and application in the management of psoriasis. *Rsc Advances* 2020;10(24):14040-9. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0RA00735H>
- [45] Reinke A, Whiteside EJ, Windus L, Desai D, Stehr E, Rad ZF. The advantages of microneedle patches compared to conventional needle-based drug delivery and biopsy devices in medicine. *Biomedical Engineering Advances* 2024 Jun 3:100127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bea.2024.100127>.
- [46] Khare N, Shende P. Microneedle system: A modulated approach for penetration enhancement. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2021 Aug 3;47(8):1183-92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03639045.2021.1992421>.
- [47] Nurgali K, Jagoe RT, Abalo R. Editorial: Adverse Effects of Cancer Chemotherapy: Anything New to Improve Tolerance and Reduce Sequelae? *Front Pharmacol* 2018;9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2018.00245>.
- [48] Nguyen HX, Banga AK. Delivery of Methotrexate and Characterization of Skin Treated by Fabricated PLGA Microneedles and Fractional Ablative Laser. *Pharm Res* 2018;35:68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-018-2369-6>.
- [49] Ma Y, Gill HS. Coating Solid Dispersions on Microneedles via a Molten Dip-Coating Method: Development and In Vitro Evaluation for Transdermal Delivery of a Water-Insoluble Drug. *J Pharm Sci* 2014;103:3621–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.24159>.
- [50] Jung YS, Koo D-H, Yang J-Y, Lee H-Y, Park J-H, Park JH. Peri-tumor administration of 5-fluorouracil sol-gel using a hollow microneedle for treatment of gastric cancer. *Drug Deliv* 2018;25:872–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10717544.2018.1455760>.
- [51] Madukwe JC. Overcoming drug resistance in cancer. *Cell* 2023;186:1515–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2023.03.019>.
- [52] Wilczyński B, Dąbrowska A, Kulbacka J, Baczyńska D. Chemoresistance and the tumor microenvironment: the critical role of cell–cell communication. *Cell Communication and Signaling* 2024;22:486. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12964-024-01857-7>.
- [53] Liu M, Jiang J, Wang Y, Liu H, Lu Y, Wang X. Smart drug delivery and responsive microneedles for wound healing. *Mater Today Bio* 2024;29:101321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2024.101321>.
- [54] Chu H, Xue J, Yang Y, Zheng H, Luo D, Li Z. Advances of Smart Stimulus-Responsive Microneedles in Cancer Treatment. *Small Methods* 2024;8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202301455>.
- [55] Ghoshal A, Mallick J, Sarkar S, Ghosh S, Ghosh B, Sarkar S. Efflux Pumps In Antimicrobial Resistance: Mechanism, Regulation And Therapeutic Implications. *Journal of Advanced Zoology* 2023. <https://doi.org/10.53555/jaz.v44iS5.3282>.
- [56] Rajabi F, Smith R, Liu-Bordes W-Y, Schertzer M, Huet S, Londoño-Vallejo A. DNA damage–induced EMT controlled by the PARP-dependent chromatin remodeler ALC1 promotes DNA repair efficiency through RAD51 in tumor cells. *Mol Biol Cell* 2024;35. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.E24-08-0370>.
- [57] Madukwe JC. Overcoming drug resistance in cancer. *Cell* 2023;186:1515–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2023.03.019>.
- [58] Biray Avcı C, Goker Bagca B, Nikanfar M, Takanlou LS, Takanlou MS, Nourazarian A. Tumor microenvironment and cancer metastasis: molecular mechanisms and therapeutic implications. *Front Pharmacol* 2024;15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2024.1442888>.
- [59] Wilczyński B, Dąbrowska A, Kulbacka J, Baczyńska D. Chemoresistance and the tumor microenvironment: the critical role of cell–cell communication. *Cell Communication and Signaling* 2024;22:486. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12964-024-01857-7>.

- [60] Makkouk A, Weiner GJ. Cancer Immunotherapy and Breaking Immune Tolerance: New Approaches to an Old Challenge. *Cancer Res* 2015;75:5–10. <https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-14-2538>.
- [61] Leone M, Mönkäre J, Bouwstra JA, Kersten G. Dissolving Microneedle Patches for Dermal Vaccination. *Pharm Res* 2017;34:2223–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-017-2223-2>.
- [62] Wang D, Wang T, Liu J, Yu H, Jiao S, Feng B, et al. Acid-Activatable Versatile Micelleplexes for PD-L1 Blockade-Enhanced Cancer Photodynamic Immunotherapy. *Nano Lett* 2016;16:5503–13. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.6b01994>.
- [63] Zaric M, Lyubomska O, Touzelet O, Poux C, Al-Zahrani S, Fay F, et al. Skin Dendritic Cell Targeting via Microneedle Arrays Laden with Antigen-Encapsulated Poly-D, L-Lactide-co-Glycolide Nanoparticles Induces Efficient Antitumor and Antiviral Immune Responses. *ACS Nano* 2013;7:2042–55. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn304235j>.
- [64] Chen S-X, Ma M, Xue F, Shen S, Chen Q, Kuang Y, et al. Construction of microneedle-assisted co-delivery platform and its combining photodynamic/immunotherapy. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2020;324:218–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2020.05.006>.
- [65] Ali AA, McCrudden CM, McCaffrey J, McBride JW, Cole G, Dunne NJ, et al. DNA vaccination for cervical cancer; a novel technology platform of RALA mediated gene delivery via polymeric microneedles. *Nanomedicine* 2017;13:921–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2016.11.019>.
- [66] Zhou Z, Pang J, Wu X, Wu W, Chen X, Kong M. Reverse immune suppressive microenvironment in tumor draining lymph nodes to enhance anti-PD1 immunotherapy via nanovaccine complexed microneedle. *Nano Res* 2020;13:1509–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-020-2737-5>.
- [67] Szewczyk-Roszczenko O, Barlev NA. The Role of p53 in Nanoparticle-Based Therapy for Cancer. *Cells* 2023;12:2803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells12242803>.
- [68] Matsuo K, Yokota Y, Zhai Y, Quan Y-S, Kamiyama F, Mukai Y, et al. A low-invasive and effective transcutaneous immunization system using a novel dissolving microneedle array for soluble and particulate antigens. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2012;161:10–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2012.01.033>.
- [69] Matsuo K, Hirobe S, Okada N, Nakagawa S. Frontiers of transcutaneous vaccination systems: Novel technologies and devices for vaccine delivery. *Vaccine* 2013;31:2403–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2013.03.022>.
- [70] Hamdy S, Haddadi A, Hung RW, Lavasanifar A. Targeting dendritic cells with nano-particulate PLGA cancer vaccine formulations. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 2011;63:943–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2011.05.021>.
- [71] Ai X, Yang J, Liu Z, Guo T, Feng N. Recent progress of microneedles in transdermal immunotherapy: A review. *Int J Pharm* 2024;662:124481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2024.124481>.
- [72] Salih OS, Al-akkam EJ. Microneedles as A Magical Technology to facilitate Transdermal Drug Delivery: A Review Article. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DRUG DELIVERY TECHNOLOGY* 2022;12:896–901. <https://doi.org/10.25258/ijddt.12.2.76>.
- [73] Menon I, Bagwe P, Gomes KB, Bajaj L, Gala R, Uddin MN, et al. Microneedles: A New Generation Vaccine Delivery System. *Micromachines (Basel)* 2021;12:435. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi12040435>.
- [74] Fujiyama T, Oze I, Yagi H, Hashizume H, Matsuo K, Hino R, et al. Induction of cytotoxic T cells as a novel independent survival factor in malignant melanoma with percutaneous peptide immunization. *J Dermatol Sci* 2014;75:43–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdermsci.2014.04.005>.
- [75] Sun X, Zeng L, Huang Y. Transcutaneous delivery of DNA/mRNA for cancer therapeutic vaccination. *J Gene Med* 2019;21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgm.3089>.
- [76] McCaffrey J, Donnelly RF, McCarthy HO. Microneedles: an innovative platform for gene delivery. *Drug Deliv Transl Res* 2015;5:424–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13346-015-0243-1>.
- [77] Chen X. Current and future technological advances in transdermal gene delivery. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 2018;127:85–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2017.12.014>.

- [78] Duong HTT, Yin Y, Thambi T, Nguyen TL, Giang Phan VH, Lee MS, et al. Smart vaccine delivery based on microneedle arrays decorated with ultra-pH-responsive copolymers for cancer immunotherapy. *Biomaterials* 2018;185:13–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2018.09.008>.
- [79] Pearton M, Saller V, Coulman SA, Gateley C, Anstey A V., Zarnitsyn V, et al. Microneedle delivery of plasmid DNA to living human skin: Formulation coating, skin insertion and gene expression. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2012;160:561–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2012.04.005>.
- [80] González-González E, Kim Y-C, Speaker TJ, Hickerson RP, Spitler R, Birchall JC, et al. Visualization of plasmid delivery to keratinocytes in mouse and human epidermis. *Sci Rep* 2011;1:158. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep00158>.
- [81] Kumar S, Shukla R. Advancements in microneedle technology: current status and next-generation innovations. *J Microencapsul* 2024;41:782–803. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652048.2024.2418613>.
- [82] Amini J, Pourmadadi M, Abedi M, Yazdian F, Rahdar A, Díez-Pascual AM. PVA-PVP-montmorillonite nanocomposite for efficient delivery of doxorubicin to breast cancer cells. *Inorg Chem Commun* 2024;162:112180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2024.112180>.
- [83] Yang P, Song H, Qin Y, Huang P, Zhang C, Kong D, et al. Engineering Dendritic-Cell-Based Vaccines and PD-1 Blockade in Self-Assembled Peptide Nanofibrous Hydrogel to Amplify Antitumor T-Cell Immunity. *Nano Lett* 2018;18:4377–85. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.8b01406>.
- [84] Martínez-Puente DH, Pérez-Trujillo JJ, Zavala-Flores LM, García-García A, Villanueva-Olivo A, Rodríguez-Rocha H, et al. Plasmid DNA for Therapeutic Applications in Cancer. *Pharmaceutics* 2022;14:1861. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14091861>.
- [85] Islam N, Richard D. Inhaled Micro/Nanoparticulate Anticancer Drug Formulations: An Emerging Targeted Drug Delivery Strategy for Lung Cancers. *Curr Cancer Drug Targets* 2019;19:162–78. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568009618666180525083451>.
- [86] <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>
- [87] Creelman B, Frivold C, Jessup S, Saxon G, Jarrahan C. Manufacturing readiness assessment for evaluation of the microneedle array patch industry: an exploration of barriers to full-scale manufacturing. *Drug Deliv Transl Re* 2022 Feb 1:1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13346-021-01076-4>